
**THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF PROVERBS WITH ZOONYM
COMPONENT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

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Abstract: This paper explores the structural analysis of proverbs featuring zoonym concepts in both English and Uzbek languages. Zoonyms, which refer to animal names and used metaphorically in language, provide a rich source for cross-linguistic and cross-cultural comparison. In the study, it is applied a comparative approach to analyze the linguistic structures of zoonymic proverbs in these two languages. Through a detailed examination of selected proverbs, the study explains how cultural and ecological factors influence the representation of animals in metaphorical expressions. Furthermore, the research investigates the grammatical patterns, figurative meanings, and cultural connotations associated with zoonymic proverbs in English and Uzbek, explaining the complex interplay between language, culture, and cognition. The findings contribute to the understanding of proverbial expressions and cultural representations in linguistic discourse, offering insights into the universality and cultural specificity of zoonymic metaphors across different linguistic systems.

Key words: zoonyms, linguoculture, proverbs, structural analysis, zoonymic metaphors.

INTRODUCTION

Zoonyms typically refer to a name or term used to identify an animal species, and they can provide insights into the relationships between humans and animals, as well as cultural attitudes and beliefs about various species. Many scientists have studied zoonyms from various subfields so far in order to understand how different languages classify and categorize animals, as well as how cultural and historical factors influence naming conventions. Zoonyms are often used metaphorically in phraseological units, like proverbs and play main role in the field of phraseology and linguoculturology. Zoonyms are main part of national linguistic picture of the world. Therefore, the study of zoonymic vocabulary is an urgent problem in modern linguistics, according to some scientists. V.N.Telia notes that animal names, as nominative units of language, “directly or indirectly, through their cultural connotations, they are connected with the spiritual and material culture of people”[1]. N.V.Podolskaya emphasizes that a zoonym is a nickname of animals assigned by

people, a sequence of characters[1]. O.V.Galimova assumes that “A zoonym is a lexico-semantic variant of a word acting a generic name of an animal, and metaphorical naming in the analysis of vocabulary from the point of view of human characteristics”[1]. In order to represent his character, behaviour, emotions, states, physical appearance, human compares with an animal which is closest to him. Zoonyms are significant fund of phraseological units of every language. Omer Beecher notes that zoomorphic phraseological units are actively used in speech and have pronounced national-cultural semantics, which determines the need for their assimilation. Moreover, zoonyms play a significant role in shaping the structure and content of proverbs, adding richness and cultural context to these traditional forms of wisdom.

METHODOLOGY

Firstly, it is identified proverbs in each language that contain zoonyms and made a list of proverbs in this field. And it is compared the similarities and differences in structural elements such as syntax, morphology and semantics. It is discussed any challenges encountered during the comparative analysis and how they were addressed. In order to make a list of proverbs, it is used related articles, proverb dictionaries of two languages such as Oxford Dictionary of proverbs, Concise dictionary of proverbs, O’zbek xalq maqollari, Nega shunday deymiz, internet sites and so on.

DISCUSSION

Zoonyms can influence the structure of proverbs in several ways. People often use zoonyms metaphorically in proverbs to express wisdom, morals or cultural values. For instance, in English, “*As busy as a bee*” uses the zoonym “*bee*” to metaphorically describe someone who is very industrious or hardworking[2]. In Uzbek culture, “*ant*” is the symbol of being hardworking as “*hardworking ant (mehnatkash chumoli)*”. In Uzbek culture the ant is an equivalent of the bee when it is used metaphorically to express being hardworking. Zoonyms can also symbolize specific cultural values or beliefs, and this symbolism is reflected in proverbs. Every country has its own cultural identity which is influenced by several factors such as religion, language, nationality and so on. For example, English people consider dogs as royal grateful, strong and loyal animals. The proverbs like “*A live dog is better than a dead lion*”, “*Feed a dog for three days and he will remember your kindness for three years*”, “*Every dog has his day*”[3]. According to Uzbek culture, most people consider this animal as inferior, unintelligent and ungrateful ones and this concept can easily be seen in Uzbek proverbs like “*It itligini qilmay qo’ymaydi (bad people always do bad things anyway)*”, “*It dan yaxshilik chiqmas (do not look forward any goodness from bad people)*”[4].

Structural analysis of proverbs with zoonym (animal name) components in English and Uzbek languages involves examining the syntactic and semantic structures of these proverbs, as well as understanding their cultural connotations. Here are some key points to consider in this analysis:

1. Syntax:

- English: English proverbs often follow a subject-verb-object structure or other common sentence structures. For example, "A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush"[2]. - Uzbek: Uzbek proverbs may follow different syntactic patterns due to the agglutinative nature of the language.

2. Parallelism: - Both languages use parallel structures to emphasize the message. For example, in English, "As the crow flies" and in Uzbek, "Suv ko‘rgan baliqday" (Like a fish that sees water).

3. Rhyme and Rhythm: - Rhyming and rhythmic patterns are common in proverbs of both languages, aiding memorability and oral transmission. In English: "Let sleeping dogs lie." In Uzbek: "Qush uyasida ko‘rganini qiladi" (The bird does what it sees in the nest)[4].

It can be an independent sentence or a part of a compound sentence both English and Uzbek. It is clear that sentences are divided into 4 groups according to representing purpose: *declarative, interrogative, imperative and exclamatory* in both languages. Most of the proverbs were made as declarative sentences. For instance, “*A fool’s bolt is soon shot*”, “*Every dog has his day*”, “*It hurar, karvon o‘tar*” and so on. However, there are some proverbs that were made as imperative, “*Don’t cast your pearls before swine*”, “*Podadan oldin chang chiqarma*”.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the structural analysis of proverbs in English and Uzbek languages reveals distinct syntactic patterns, semantic richness, and deep cultural roots. While both languages use proverbs to impart wisdom and reflect human nature, their structural forms and cultural contexts provide unique insights into the societies they originate from. Understanding these structures helps appreciate the linguistic beauty and cultural significance embedded in proverbs.

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